

Coordination Complex of Quinine with Ferrous Sulphate

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Quinine forms 1 : 1 complex with ferrous sulphate in alcoholic solutions as indicated by conductometric, spectrophotometric and analytical data. A structure supported by I.R. data is assigned to the complex.

FERROUS iron in various forms has long been used in Aurvedic, Unani and Apathic medicines, particularly in anaemic conditions. Therefore in continuation of our work¹ on the cobalt complexes of cinchonine and quinine, herein we describe ferrous sulphate complex with quinine.

Results and Discussion

Composition of the complex

(a) Standard solutions of ferrous sulphate (B.D.H.; 0.01M) and quinine base (B.D.H.; 0.005M) were prepared in spectroscopically pure 80% methanol. 10 ml of the ligand was diluted to 200 ml. and titrated against the metal solution using 'Toshniwal' conductivity bridge and dip type electrodes at 19°. The results, after volume corrections indicate 1 : 1 and 2 : 1 quinine ferrous sulphate complex formation

(b) The nature of the complex was studied spectrophotometrically on 'Spekol' using Vosburgh and Cooper² method. For this mixtures containing 2 : 1, 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 proportions of equimolar solutions of ferrous sulphate and quinine ($10.0 \times 10^{-4}M$) in spectroscopically pure methanol were taken and the absorbances measured. The results indicated that only one complex is formed.

(c) Formation of 1 : 1 complex was further confirmed by the Job's method of continuous variation³

Fig. 1(A). $a_1 = 0.83 \times 10^{-7}M$; $b_1 = 4.16 \times 10^{-7}M$; $a_2 = 0.83 \times 10^{-7}M$; $b_2 = 3.16 \times 10^{-7}M$ wave length 358; temp. 28°.

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and the mole ratio method⁴, using absorbance as the index property. The results are given in Figs. 1(A) and 1(B)

Fig. 1(B). Ligand and metal 0.0005 molar (curve A, A') Ligand and metal 0.0004 molar (curve B, B') Wave lengths 358 and 375; temp. 29°.

Isolation and analysis

Quinine base 1.50 g (1 mole) was dissolved in methyl alcohol and ferrous sulphate 1.28 g (1 mole) was dissolved in minimum quantity of water. Two drops of H_2SO_4 were added to stabilize divalent iron. The two solutions were mixed and cooled in an ice bath for 4 hr. The complex was filtered and washed with ether. A green coloured complex turned brick red after drying. Yield 1.2 g, m.p. 230°. Under these conditions 2 : 1 complex could not be isolated.

Found : Fe, 10.62; SO_4 , 18.50; N, 5.00 and H_2O , 4.12; while $C_{20}H_{24}O_2N_2 \cdot FeSO_4 \cdot H_2O$ requires Fe, 11.31; SO_4 , 19.45; N, 5.67 and H_2O , 3.64%.

The composition of quinine-ferrous sulphate complex is analogous to the compositions of cinchonine and quinine complexes of cobalt chloride¹ and hence a similar structure (I) may be assigned to it, considering the fact that each of the two nitrogens and the oxygen of the secondary alcoholic group in the molecule of quinine are capable of donation.

(I)

Structure (I) gets support from that fact that in the I.R. spectra (which will form part of later communication), the metal-nitrogen absorption band is observed at 650 cm^{-1} and metal-oxygen absorption

band at 660 cm^{-1} . Further, bands at 820, 3180 and 3420 cm^{-1} indicate coordinated water molecule, while bands at 1200 and 1350 cm^{-1} indicate presence of bonded sulphate.

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